

A Research on Students' Views on Electronic Recreation Activities and Level of Fear of Missing Out

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to determine the participation of students in electronic recreation activities and their level of fear of missing out. As a research method, the survey, as a quantitative method, was applied. The population of the research consists of 12664 students studying at Sinop University. A questionnaire was applied to 260 of the students. As a result of the study, it has been determined that electronic recreation activities are more preferred for socializing and it is seen that the level of fear of missing out on those who participate in these electronic recreation activities is not high in general.

1. Introduction

In recent years, with the development of the internet and its use by everyone, it has been observed that the information flow and interaction between societies has increased in the world. In addition to this flow of information and interaction, it would be very accurate to talk about the changes in people's lifestyles and perspectives on their lives with the new developments in information communication and technologies. With these innovations in information communication and technologies, the world has become global and almost inclined to eliminate borders. On the other hand, it would not be wrong to talk about the significant changes in consumer demands and expectations with these technological developments.

These developments and innovations in the field of technology have direct and permanent effects on the tourism sector in every respect. Today, advances in information communication and technologies transform tourism significantly in parallel with these innovations, and it is seen that it is effective in many areas from consumers' preferences and demands to operation management (Guttentag, 2010: 637).

With technological and industrial developments, the monotony of daily life, intense work tempo, wear people out spiritually and physically (Arni & Khairil,

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2013). People have entered into new searches in order to regain their lost energy in working life, protect their health and increase their quality of life (Dorul, 2017; Çavdar & Yıldız, 2020). Electronic recreation is turning into a multidisciplinary phenomenon that is newly formed as a concept and can contain many different disciplines. With the acceleration of developments in technology and informatics, it is seen that it has become a position that has increased its popularity and that people can easily reach in their daily lives. However, the concept of electronic recreation is growing day by day and its place in people's lives is increasing with the economic dimension it has created with academic studies and sectoral meaning. It is seen that the limited time that people can spare for recreational activities due to their busy work and life pace makes it easier for them to prefer electronic recreation activities as an activity. It is known that young people show more interest in electronic recreation activities. However, young people who spend time in these environments should also follow the updates in these environments. This situation increases the importance of another concept: fear of missing out. In this context, the aim of the study is to determine the participation of students in electronic recreation activities and their level of fear of missing out.

2. Literature Review

Recent developments in technology, with the effect of many sectors, cause the emergence of a digital dimension that can be an alternative to physical reality. In his study, Bryce (2001) stated that information communication technologies and the internet have created new areas for participation in leisure activities, and as a result, contemporary leisure activities have emerged at a level that can change leisure concepts and organizations. Leisure activities with technological devices can also perform the same functions as traditional leisure activities (Mokhtarian et al., 2006: 263).

Especially with the emergence of the concept of Industry 4.0, many activities have been moved to virtual environments. Industry 1.0 "mechanization in production", Industry 2.0 "mass production" and Industry 3.0 as "quantity and automation in production" can be briefly expressed. (Arıkan et al., 2021: 22). The widespread of computer use with Industry 3.0 has provided computer and console games to have new-time recreative activities and initiated the digital recreation period. In this period, e-sports, e-book concepts have also appeared with the internet. (Bayram & Kavlak, 2021: 389). However, the Industrial 4.0 period carries recreation activities to a different dimension. E-sports that defined by Bayram (2018) as "computer, game console and mobile devices based sports activity on amateur and professional competition based on mobile devices", is especially with the development of translating interaction, it has experienced a great change. With virtual reality applications, which are still developing and spreading, individuals can perform many recreational activities that they want to participate and do in digital environments. While it is possible to carry out recreational activities in completely digital environments with virtual reality applications, augmented reality applications

that can combine virtual and real environments also allow recreational activities to be done. Thus, e-recreation concept that defined by Bayram and Kavlak (2021: 395) as “performing recreational activities in electronic environments” is emerged. Bucher and Bucher (1974) defined the concept of recreation as “a person gets rid of the boringness of daily life by participating in social, cultural and sports activities that are suitable for his/her self and enjoys doing, and gaining a social personality by interacting with other people and they emphasized the general and social aspect of the concept”. The concept of e-recreation allows all of these activities to be made in electronic and online environments. The opinion of the e-recreation activities wouldn't replace the traditional recreational activities of is a little bit weaker every day. With the concepts of virtual reality, augmented reality and metaverse, physical presence and virtual environment are tried to be combined and serious developments are experienced in this regard.

There are studies showing that electronic recreation activities improve individuals mentally. For example, in his research, Prensky (2012) found that individuals participating in e-sports, an electronic recreation activity, significantly improved their problem-solving skills. In addition to these skills, Jackson et al. (2012), in their study, that the games played on digital platforms with electronic recreation activities increase the creativity capacity of individuals, whether they contain violence or not. In addition, as the simplest example, simulation-based game consoles with motion-sensing sensors also allow physical development.

Technological developments can provide very easy and very fast access to real-time activities such as various activities, lectures, recreational activities, especially for young people. During these activities, young people share information, follow updates and socialize. This constant updating and monitoring behavior, especially fed by online activities, is called fear of Missing Out (FoMO) all over the world. FoMO, (Fear of Missing Out), is anxiety about feeling deprived of rewarding experiences that others have had (Erçiş et al., 2021: 223). FoMO, which is also defined as a kind of anxiety disorder, can occur in all environments where people communicate. Due to the establishment of a social environment while electronic recreation activities are taking place, the probability of the emergence of FoMO can be seen as high.

3. Methodology

The aim of the study is to determine the participation of students in electronic recreation activities and their level of fear of missing out. As a research method, the survey, as a quantitative method, was applied. The population of the research consists of 12664 students studying at Sinop University. A questionnaire was applied to 260 of the students. For the questions of “Reasons for Preferring Electronic Recreation Activities” and “Effects of Electronic Recreation Activities” Binarbaşı (2006)'s research scale was used. For the questions of “Fear of Missing Out” Przybylski et a. (2013)'s research scale was used. Collected data was analyzed by means of a programme. The reliability coefficient as Cronbach's Alpha: for the scale

of Reasons for Preferring Electronic Recreation Activities 0,854; scale of Effects of Electronic Recreation Activities 0,887; scale of Fear of Missing Out: 0,819 was calculated.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of participants. As shown, most participants (62.3%) were female and the majority (73.1%) was middle income range. 25% of the participants School of Tourism and Hotel Management, 18.5% of the participants Faculty of Arts and Science and 15,8 % of the participants Faculty of Education have education. Most participants (54,6%) choosed social activities for their free times. As shown in Table 1, 29,2% of the participants had 21 hours or more free time for week and the majority (67.7%) was indicated difficulty in making use of free time for sometimes.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of participants

		n	%			n	%
Gender	Female	162	62,3	Income	Low	45	17,3
	Male	98	37,7		Middle	190	73,1
Faculty	School of Tourism and Hotel Management	65	25,0		High	25	9,6
	Faculty of Theology	32	12,3	Type of event	Sporting activities	48	18,5
	Faculty of Arts and Science	48	18,5		Social activities	142	54,6
	Faculty of Education	41	15,8		Cultural and artistic activities	39	15,0
	Faculty of Health Science	30	11,5		Others	31	11,9
	Others	44	16,9	Class	1st Class	57	21,9
Weekly free time	1-5 hours	29	11,2		2nd Class	86	33,1
	6-10 hours	58	22,3		3rd Class	78	30,0
	11-15 hours	58	22,3		4th Class	39	15,0
	16-20 hours	39	15,0	Difficulty in making use of free time	Always	37	14,2
	21 hours or more	76	29,2		Sometimes	176	67,7
			Never		47	18,1	

Source: Authors' elaboration

Table 2 presents the average of opinions on reasons for preferring electronic recreation activities. According to Table 2, participants prefer electronic recreation activities mostly to relax and get away from the work environment (3,68), to provide a nice environment" (3,61) and I can be with my friends (3,51). The expressions with the least average are "I have weight problem" (2,29), "To regain my health" (2,92) and "It has become a habit" and "To keep this habit" (2,98).

Table 2. Reasons for preferring electronic recreation activities

Reasons for preferring electronic recreation activities	\bar{X}	S.S.
Because.....		
It suits my abilities and it is the best I can	3,15	1,284
I can be with my friends	3,51	1,212
It doesn't require me to spend a lot of money	3,43	1,314
There is no environmental and family pressure that will prevent me from participating in the activities	3,29	1,405
To relax and get away from the work environment	3,68	1,166
I can easily reach the activity center	3,38	1,260
To provide a nice environment	3,61	1,174
Sufficient facilities and equipment related to the activity areas I want to operate	3,39	1,243
Having programs prepared for the activity areas that I want to operate	3,38	1,128
Orientation of my education	3,20	1,261
To protect my health	3,06	1,354
To regain my health	2,92	1,347
I have weight problem	2,29	1,406
It has become a habit and to keep this habit	2,98	1,319

Source: Authors' elaboration

Table 3 present the effects of electronic recreation activities. According to table, the expressions with the highest average left by the participants of e-Recreation activities are "Prevents boredom" (3,70), "Satisfying and enjoyable" (3,68) and "Fun and exiting" (3,58). The expressions with the least average are "Healthy" (2,95), "Educational" (3,30) and "Relaxing" (3,36).

Table 3. Effects of electronic recreation activities

Effects of electronic recreation activities	\bar{X}	S.S.
Relaxing	3,36	1,318
Fun and exciting	3,58	1,222
Satisfying and enjoyable	3,68	1,214
Educational	3,30	1,212
Prevents boredom	3,70	1,204
Healthy	2,95	1,292
Inspiring	3,38	1,229
Socializer	3,55	1,261
Achieved social status	3,38	1,360

Source: Authors' elaboration

Table 4 present the level of fear of missing out. When the level of fear of missing out is examined, it is seen that the overall average is low. The expressions with the highest average are "When I miss out on a planned get-together it bothers me" (3,51) and "It is important that I understand my friends in jokes" (3,13). The expressions with the least average are "I fear my friends have more rewarding experiences than me" (1,97) and "I get anxious when I don't know what my friends are up to" (2,00).

Table 4. Fear of missing out

Fear of missing out	\bar{X}	S.S.
I fear others have more rewarding experiences than me.	2,01	1,206
I fear my friends have more rewarding experiences than me.	1,97	1,201
I get worried when I find out my friends are having fun without me.	2,05	1,208
I get anxious when I don't know what my friends are up to.	2,00	1,144
It is important that I understand my friends "in jokes".	3,13	1,398
Sometimes, I wonder if I spend too much time keeping up with what is going on.	2,68	1,306
It bothers me when I miss an opportunity to meet up with friends.	2,80	1,392
When I have a good time it is important for me to share the details online (e.g. updating status).	2,62	1,348
When I miss out on a planned get-together it bothers me.	3,51	1,393
When I go on vacation, I continue to keep tabs on what my friends are doing.	2,67	1,412
Overall average	2,54	,804

Source: Authors' elaboration

5. Conclusion

The development in information and communication technologies has shown itself in many parts of human life, from military industry to health, from architecture to education, from banking to manufacturing industry and transportation, and has caused significant changes in human life style and standards. These developments in technology have found their place in the tourism and recreation sectors as well as in many areas. The importance of the services provided by these technologies has been understood more due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which spread all over the world in late 2019 and early 2020. Due to the curfews announced in many cities in countries infected with the disease, including Turkey, due to the epidemic, people had to spend time at home, and many people participated in electronic recreation activities through their devices such as computers, smartphones and laptops.

As a result of the study, it has been determined that electronic recreation activities are more preferred for socializing. In addition, these activities are preferred to create a new environment and escape from the ordinariness of life. Moreover, it has been seen that the rate of preference is high because it is a more economical form of activity. According to the participants, as a result of participation in electronic recreation activities, emotions such as entertainment, relaxation and satisfaction are gained. As another perspective of the study, when the level of fear of missing out is examined, it is seen that the level of fear of missing out on those who participate in these electronic recreation activities is not high in general.

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